

PROBLEMS OF LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN 21ST CENTURY

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Abstract. *“The decisions that are being made today in the direction of education policy have a broad impact on the country's scientific, economic, political and cultural needs,” said Darya columnist, expert of the Great Future Group, Busan, South Korea. Professor of the University of Languages Azamat Akbarov. The system of teaching foreign languages to children at an early age, which has been introduced in some countries of the world since the 1990s, is also in line with our country, and in 2017-2018 it was proposed to adopt some legislation in this area.*

Keywords: *foreign language, students' level, interlingual interaction, listening comprehension, speaking, reading, writing and vocabulary acquisition.*

ПРОБЛЕМЫ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА В 21 ВЕКЕ

Аннотация. *«Решения, которые принимаются сегодня в направлении образовательной политики, имеют широкое влияние на научные, экономические, политические и культурные потребности страны», — сказала обозревателю Дарья, эксперт группы «Великое будущее», Пусан, Южная Корея. Профессор Университета языков Азамат Акбаров. Система обучения детей иностранным языкам в раннем возрасте, которая внедряется в некоторых странах мира с 1990-х годов, также соответствует нашей стране, и в 2017-2018 годах было предложено принять некоторые законодательные акты в этой сфере.*

Ключевые слова: *иностраннный язык, уровень учащихся, межъязыковое взаимодействие, аудирование, говорение, чтение, письмо и приобретение словарного запаса.*

INTRODUCTION

“Everyone has the right to acquire knowledge»

Article 41 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Any child who demonstrates a normal level of development is able to learn any language they encounter in the environment in which they live and has the potential to communicate with others. Reducing the number of **languages** a child can learn from a neurological point of view is not the topic of our conversation. On the contrary, every child without a pathological defect can learn two, three or more languages. However, a child's level of proficiency in each language varies from one language to another, depending on the need to use that language and the environment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Many studies today show that the success of foreign language teaching in childhood is achieved if it is carried out with appropriate methods and approaches. However, this can only be achieved through the use of language teaching methods and teaching materials that are appropriate to the students' level of learning. There are two main conditions: the student's ability

to communicate in a foreign language environment and the use of the foreign language being taught, and the use of the language being taught in meaningful contexts.

RESULTS

As in our country, in systems where a foreign language is limited only by the scope of the course, the time and speed at which the language is taught is important. 5-7 years to acquire knowledge of listening comprehension, speaking, reading, writing and vocabulary acquisition and to apply all these skills in a foreign language from an academic point of view correctly and flawlessly. There should be a curriculum that provides for regular and effective classes. From this point of view, a week of foreign language classes in grades 2, 3 and 4 is not enough. Language teaching, which is a natural means of both written and oral communication, requires continuity. A 7-8 year old elementary school student may not be able to master a foreign language system that is only available for 4-5 hours a week and cannot be used in their own environment.

Another serious problem in language teaching is the methods and equipment used to teach the language. When examining the textbooks used at the primary school level in public schools, it is clear that there is no connection between the components between the subjects and no connection between the units of vocabulary despite the myriad of vocabularies. In fact, when we use language in every situation in life, every word that comes out of our mouth is semantically connected with what is said before or after. At a time when technology is rapidly evolving, there is no doubt that textbooks should not be the only source of language teaching. If we consider that in 80% of cases our teachers use textbooks in teaching foreign languages across the country, it is necessary to pay special attention to the preparation of other books and additional teaching materials. Today, we are in a situation where a 7-8 year old child who started learning a foreign language in the 2nd grade of primary school came to the end of the 4th grade last week or last night in a language that he or she has been learning for 3 years. cannot tell the action that took place. Because the content of the textbooks used in primary school does not allow it.

DISCUSSION

In the early stages of learning a foreign language, the influence of students' mother tongue characteristics can be observed. This situation, called "interlingual interaction", indicates that there is always a connection between the native language in the student's memory and the other language in which he or she began to learn. Also, many aspects of language development are slow in language learning. Some features and aspects of language are learned earlier and some later. Sometimes it takes a long time to learn many seemingly simple things because of differences between languages. If a student does not have the opportunity to hear and use the language, he or she will not be able to make positive progress in language learning and will soon forget what he or she has already learned.

CONCLUSIONS

Each material presented in language learning should be meaningful and the topics should be linked to each other and, if necessary, linked to what the child has learned in other lessons. In this case, foreign language teachers are required to work together and make plans together with other teachers who teach the given class. It also requires taking into account and relating each student's experience and life to the learning process. In this context, content-based models and fairy tales and songs can be used in the teaching process that are relevant to the levels of cognitive, linguistic and social development and activities in which students are directly

involved. In short, given that more than half of the world's population speaks two or more languages in their daily lives, we are convinced that learning a foreign language is not a miracle. In addition, we can teach a foreign language to a student not only as an opportunity for a few people to succeed, but also so that they can keep pace with the times.

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